

BREAST CANCER KNOWLEDGE AND BREAST SELF-EXAMINATION PRACTICES AMONG FEMALE OF A COMMUNITY OF LAHORE: A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Breast cancer is an unusual growth of tumor-like structure in the milk-producing gland or duct that transfers milk to nipples. Breast cancer is the most common cancer found in females around the world. It also a primary cause of death in the whole world. Breast cancer is a world wide issue.

Methodology :A cross-sectional design was used in this study. The research was conducted in the community of Lahore. The target population is the females of the community. The sample size was collected through the Solwin formula which comes out 149.

Results : 11.4% of females have a low level of knowledge regarding breast cancer.59.7% of females have intermediate knowledge and only 28.8% of females have a high level of knowledge.

Conclusion

The knowledge about breast cancer was intermediate mostly women knows about the risk factor that causes breast cancer. The knowledge about breast cancer signs and the symptom was also good mostly females know about it and their practices were average.

Introduction

Breast cancer is an unusual growth of tumor-like structure in the milk-producing gland or duct that transfers milk to nipples. (Birhane et al., 2017) Breast cancer is the most common cancer found in females around the world. It also a primary cause of death in the whole world. Breast cancer is a world wide issue. (Akram, Iqbal, Daniyal, & Khan, 2017). Breast cancer affects both developing and developed countries. At least one million women were diagnosed with breast cancer annually. 40000 females died due to this cancer. The cases of breast cancer are increasing in Pakistan like other developing countries. One out of nine female is at risk of forming breast cancer. (Rasool et al., 2019) More than 17000 deaths occurred due to breast cancer in Pakistan. In the list of world health organization, Pakistan placed on number 9

because of the highest rates of death due to breast cancer. WHO. Health Profile of Pakistan: WHO; 2017 Breast cancer rapidly spread throughout the world. (Rasool et al., 2019) it attacks women in their most fertile times. The factor that causes breast cancer is old age, family history of breast cancer, and women with early menstruation and late menopause they are also on the risk of developing breast cancer. (Sama et al., 2017) Breast cancer can be control in its early stages but the advanced stage of cancer is difficult to treat and too expensive. (Birhane et al., 2017). Screening is prose to find cancer in the early stages or before any symptoms. (Agarwal, 2018) Early finding of breast cancer helps to control cancer and further disease progression. The best way to detect breast cancer in the early stages is breast self-examination, clinical breast examination, and mammography. Breast self-

examination is the best and easy way to detect breast cancer than in the other two methods. Breast self-examination is costless and available everywhere. BSE helps to diagnose cancer and also useful for initial stage treatment (Lee*, 2018) Breast self-examination is very important for a female to understand the normal shape of the breast. She is the first person who notices the changes in their breast. (Esen, Aslan, Sonbahar, & Kerimoğlu, 2018)

How to perform breast self-examination.

Look

Stand in front of the mirror to examine for breast. Look your breast for three sides right-left and front. Assess for any type of bruises and scars.

Raise arms above the head and places them on the hip line to examine breasts while bending a little bit forward.

Firstly assess the shape of the breast compares one breast to another one. Usually, one breast is more extensive than the other. But there should be no sudden changes in shape.

Then go for the skin assessment. Look for any kind of skin rash, color changes, redness, orange color texture, dimpling, or contraction in size.

Check nipples for any type of physical changes like changes in color, redness, nipple inversion, itching, inflammation, scaliness, or secretion.

Look for any noticeable changes in size and pattern of veins and their numbers in any or both breasts.

Palpate

Palpate the breasts by using the three middle finger pads, not by the tips of these fingers, in the form of circles of about dime. For every round, there is a change in pressure. So tissue of the breast can be felt under the pads.

Start to palpate your breast from the exterior side of the breast smoothly move your fingers in a circle. Slowly moves towards the nipples. Be sure that you covered the whole breast.

Apply little force and again start to palpate from the outer side to the inner side and then move your finger's outer side.

At the end of the breast, self-examination moves your finger up to downward in a circular motion. Then move your finger slowly upward. Be sure that you covered the whole breast. (Agarwal, 2018)

Current recommendations from the American college of obstetricians and gynecologists

- 40 to 50 or older women need screening and mammography every year.
- Breast self-awareness helps to discover palpable breast cancer.
- 19 years and older females need clinical breast self-examination every year.
- According to the American cancer society, women needs to aware of any changes in her breast.

Clinical breast examination

In clinical breast examination doctors and health care professionals examine the breast. The doctor carefully examines the breast and underarms for lumps. Women should be done this process every 2 to 3 years starting at the age of 20 or beginning at the age of 40.

5 Points of self-awareness

- Remember that what is healthy for you.
- Remember what changes to observe and consider.
- Observe and consider.
- If you find any changes, report to your doctor immediately.
- Go for mammography at least once in 2 years from the starting the age of 40.

Objectives

Determine the knowledge about breast cancer among community females.

Assess the practices regarding breast self-examination among community females.

Purpose

The purpose of the study to identify the knowledge about breast self-examination and also check their practices regarding breast self-examination.

Significance of the study

The study is helpful to increase the knowledge of community females about breast cancer. This study also enhances their practices regarding breast self-examination that help them to understand their breast structure or any abnormalities that affect their breast.

Research question

What is the participant's awareness regarding breast cancer?

What are the participant's practices regarding breast self-examination?

Literature Review

In 2016 a study was conducted on university female students in Uganda. According to that study, the knowledge about breast cancer and breast self-examination was very high among them but the level of practice was very low. Students get information about breast cancer and breast self-examination from social media. (Godfrey, Agatha, & Nankumbi, 2016) A cross-sectional study was conducted on Yemeni women in 2016. About half of the community females are educated at the university level and secondary level. The women living in Aden, Yemen, whose respondents find themselves in poor awareness and insufficient BSE activities. These findings demonstrate the desperately required need for targeted, ongoing, concentrated and mandatory community-based awareness interventions to strengthen early detection and reduce the burden of breast cancer in Yemen, taking account of social and cultural backgrounds. These binding efforts should concentrate on promoting the practice of BSE among women. (Al-Sakkaf & Basaleem, 2016)

The study was conducted in Ghana in which the author states that BSE was known to most students. Half of the students had a high degree of awareness about BSE. The students thought BSE should be carried out every day, but most students conduct BSE monthly as prescribed. The students were substantially higher in University than secondary school students. In contrast with tertiary students, more secondary students never studied BSE. BSE is a healthy practice that is to be encouraged by most participants (Udoh et al., 2020)

The study was conducted in Sudan showing that poor awareness of breast cancer among prisoners has been confirmed. Also, their breast self-examination awareness and practice were poor and further initiatives for health education in such institutions have been suggested (Mohamed, Nori, Ahmed, Altamih, & Kunna, 2020) The study conducted in Ethiopia states that, a few women frequently apply BSE. In societies that have a more diversified female

population and live in remote areas of the country, awareness and practice of BSE may be considerably lower. Additional steps are required to address young women in the form of BSE awareness and advocacy campaigns to increase the risk of early diagnosis of breast cancer in Ethiopia (Dinegde, Demie, & Diriba, 2020) According to another study that BSE awareness and practice levels are very poor. This should promote efforts to spread this awareness to women. The study indicated that focused education allows healthcare staff to develop the requisite expertise and it seems that more hours can be added to university healthcare curricula about the prevention of breast cancer and BSE. Breast cancer prevention programs mainly aiming at BSE are critically essential to early detection of health problems, taught by highly qualified health professionals, especially nurses. (Sapountzi-Krepia et al., 2017) A similar study was conducted in Kashmir in which the author checked their knowledge about breast self-examination. But the results were not good due to the low level of education. Most people are illiterate and their socioeconomic status is low. In that study education and occupation has a relationship with breast cancer and breast self-examination but there is no enough relation with socioeconomic status. (Sideeq, Ayoub, & Khan, 2017) Our study concluded that our undergraduate students have good knowledge and awareness about breast cancer, its spread, risk factors, and examination. They were all very attentive to it. The point to consider is the practice they practiced about breast self-examination, which is lacking. This shows a lack of knowledge. Programs that both aim to raise screening awareness and its accessibility should therefore be implemented (Rasool et al., 2019)

Methodology**Research design**

A cross-sectional design was used in this study.

Research Setting

The research was conducted in the community of Lahore

Target population

The target population is the females of the community.

Sample size

The sample size was collected through Solvin formula which comes out. Slovin's sampling formula will be used to find the sample size of the study population. If study population is approximately = 230 ,Confidence level =95 e= Margin of error=0.05,
 $n = N / 1 + (N) (e)^2$
 $n = 230 / (1 + 230 \times 0.0025)$
 $n = 230 / 1.575$
 $n = 147$

Sampling technique

A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used in this research.

Instrument

The questionnaire was adopted from (Godfrey, Agatha, & Nankumbi, 2016). The questionnaire consists of 29 items that help us to assess the knowledge and practice of breast cancer and breast self-examination in community women. The questions were designed to "yes" and "no" or "true" and "false" responses that easy to understand.

Conceptual Knowledge

Things that a person understand through their experience

Practice

Thing or procedure that we perform again and again.

Breast cancer

Breast cancer is a disease that causes due to abnormal division of breast cells.

Operational Knowledge

The fact or condition of knowing something with familiarity gained through experience or association

Practice

The actual application or use of an idea, belief, or method, as opposed to theories relating to it.

Breast cancer

Breast cancer usually presents as a focal abnormality within the breast. (Winchester, 2006)

Questionnaire

The correct (yes and true) responses were assigned one mark each while the incorrect (no and false) responses were assigned zero or no marks. The level of knowledge was categorized as follows: low (0-7 marks), intermediate (8-14 marks), and high (15- 21 marks). The maximum score was 21 marks.

Sample selection**Inclusion criteria**

Women aged over 18 was involved in this research

Women who are willing to participate in this study.

Exclusive criteria

Absentee of females at the time of survey distribution.

Those who are not able to participate in the study due to any co morbidity

Source of data**Primary data**

Females include in this study from the selected community will be the primary source of data collection

Secondary data

Books, journals, previous researches, and the internet will be the secondary source of data collection.

Data collection procedure

1. Permission was granted from community authority.
2. The researchers has introduced themselves to participants.
3. Assign the participant through convenient sampling techniques.
4. After assigning the consent from all participants explained to them all advantages and disadvantages of the research.

Data analysis procedure

Statistical analysis of the data was completed with SPSS statistics 21. After collecting the data

transferred into SPSS for mathematical analysis .this SPSS addition eliminated human data entry and reduced the time required for data entry .it also easy to use and trustable software.

Ethical consideration

Written informed consent was attached to all forms. All information and data collection was kept confidential. Participants will remain unidentified throughout the research. The participant was informed that there are no disadvantages or risks in the procedure of the research. They were informed that they are free

to withdraw at any time during the process of the study. In a laptop, it will be kept under a password.

RESULTS

Table number 1 shows that the demographic of the participant in our study. A total of 149 participants participate in our study. The mean value of age was 40.09 and the age of menarche was 14.42. Most of the participants are educated. Their religion is Islam and most of them are married.

Demographic Data	Mean ± SD	
Age	40.09 ± 10.05	
Age at menarche	14.42±0.97	
	Frequency	
Education		
Primary	7	4.7
High	89	59.7
College	37	24.8
University	16	10.7
Religion		
Islam	149	100.0
Marital status		
Single	7	4.7
Married	142	95.3

In our study table number 2 shows the knowledge of participants regarding breast cancer. Their knowledge was good 81.2% of participants heard about breast cancer. But we always faced the myth that breast cancer only affects females suffering and in our study, 64.4% of females faced the same myth. 69.8% of females give the correct response that breast cancer cannot be transmitted from one person to another person.81.2% participant knows that old age is a cause of breast cancer .80% females knows that another cause of breast cancer is a family history of breast cancer. 75.8%participant have a response that the birth of a first child after 30 is a cause of breast cancer 69.1 % of participant response that early menses is the cause of breast cancer.72.5% of participant response that late menopause after 55 is the reason for breast cancer. 68.5% participant response that those women that start late

breastfeeding is at risk of breast cancer .53% participant response that being a female we are at risk of breast cancer.51% of the participant said that the Cigarette smoking is another factor of breast cancer.54.4% of female response that the person who takes low-fat diet was a risk on breast cancer. 55.7% of participants that the use of oral contraceptives is a cause of breast cancer .65.1% of participants responded that radiation exposure also causes breast cancer. 63.8% said that large breast is a sign of breast cancer. 67.1% of participants responded that a painless lump is a sign of breast cancer. 63.8% of participants responded that nipple discharge is another sign of cancer. 38.3% participant knows that the pain in the chest is not related to breast cancer. 61.7% of participant response that lumps under the armpit are also a sign of cancer.69.1% of participant response that change in breast shape is another sign of breast cancer.

Knowledge Questionnaire	Responses	Frequency	
Have you ever heard about breast cancer?	Yes	121	81.2
	No	28	18.8
Risk Factor Knowledge Questions			
Breast cancer affects only females.	True	96	64.4
	False	53	35.5
Breast cancer can be transmitted from one person to another.	True	45	30.2
	False	104	69.8
Old age.	Yes	121	81.2
	No	28	18.8
Family history of breast cancer.	Yes	120	80.5
	No	29	19.5
Birth of first child after the age of 30 years.	Yes	113	75.8
	No	36	24.2
Early-onset of menses (before the age of 12 years)	Yes	103	69.1
	No	46	30.9
Late menopause (after the age of 55 years).	Yes	108	72.5
	No	41	27.5
Late initiation of breastfeeding.	Yes	102	68.5
	No	47	31.5
Being a woman.	Yes	79	53.0
	No	70	47.0
Cigarette smoking.	Yes	76	51.0
	No	73	49.0
Low-fat diet.	Yes	81	54.4
	No	68	45.6
Use of oral contraceptive.	Yes	83	55.7
	No	66	44.3
Radiation exposure.	Yes	97	65.1
	No	52	34.9
Signs and Symptoms			
Large breasts.	Yes	95	63.8
	No	54	36.2
Painless breast lump.	Yes	100	67.1
	No	49	32.9
Nipple discharge.	Yes	95	63.8
	No	54	36.2
Pain in the breast region.	Yes	92	61.7
	No	57	38.3
Lump under the armpit.	Yes	92	61.7
	No	57	38.3
Change in breast shape.	Yes	103	69.1
	No	46	30.9

In our study table number 3 shows the practices of participants regarding breast self-examination 81.2% of participants heard about breast self-examination. According to our study results, 59.1% of females perform breast self-

examination. 4% of females said they start breast self-examination from next month. 10.1% of females perform breast self-examination once a month.

Breast Self-Examination (BSE) Practices			
Have you ever heard of breast self - examination?	Yes	121	81.2
	No	28	18.8
Have you ever performed a breast self-examination?	Yes	88	59.1
	No	61	40.9
If no, are you planning to perform a breast self-examination?	Yes in next month	6	4.0
	Yes not in next month	19	12.8
	No	17	11.4
	I do not know	19	12.8
If Yes, how often do you perform a breast self-examination?	Twice a week	7	4.7
	Once a month	15	10.1
	Once a week	14	9.4
	Once a year	52	34.8

Table number 4 shows that 11.4% of females have a low level of knowledge regarding breast cancer. 59.7% of females have intermediate

knowledge and only 28.8% of females have a high level of knowledge.

Level of knowledge	Range	Frequency	
Low	0-7	17	11.4
Intermediate	8-14	89	59.7
High	15-20	43	28.8

Discussion

Knowledge of breast cancer is the most important part of enhancing the practices of breast self-examination. In our study the level of knowledge was intermediate (59.7%) and 28.8% have a high level of knowledge. But the past study that was conducted in UAE only 51% of the participant has general knowledge about breast cancer (Younis, Al-Rubaye, Haddad, Hammad, & Hijazi, 2016) in our study, 81% of female heard about breast cancer. Our results are comparable with the past study that was conducted in Kampala, Uganda in which 98% of participant heard about breast cancer (Godfrey, Agatha, & Nankumbi, 2016) the study that was conducted in UAE shows that 54.6% of students know that breast cancer also affects males in our study the ratio was 35.5% participant knows that breast cancer also affects males. (Younis et al., 2016) In present study shows that 69.8% participant knows that breast cancer cannot be transmitted to one person to another. The results were comparable to another study that was conducted in Kampala, Uganda shows that 69.1% of the subjects give a correct response to this question (Godfrey, Agatha, & Nankumbi, 2016). In our study, 81.2% of participants

responded that old age is a risk factor for breast cancer. But the past study that was conducted in India in 2018 shows that only 66.6% subjects know that advance age is a risk factor (Singh et al., 2018) The present study shows that 72.5% participant knows that late menopause is the reason of breast cancer the results compared able with another study that was conducted in Bengaluru in 2017 that shows 88% participant give correct responses on it. . In our study 80.5% subjects response that breast cancer is an inherited disease and other study shows that 89% gives the correct response. (Madhukumar, Thambiran, Basavaraju, & Bedadala, 2017) In our study 51% of participant response that cigarette smoking is a reason for breast cancer but in the past study that was conducted in Cameroon shows that 58.2% of participant gives correct response (Sama et al., 2017) 69.1% of females know that early age of menses is a risk of breast cancer. But in the past study, the ratio was low only 24% of females give correct responses on it. (Godfrey, Agatha, & Nankumbi, 2016) in our study, 75.8% of participant knows that late childbirth is also a risk factor but in the past study the ratio was 46.6%. (Al-Zalabani et al., 2016) In our study 53% response that being a

woman we are at risk and in the past study the ratio was 54.4%. In the present study, 54% of participant knows that low-fat diet also a reason of breast cancer but the result was comparable with another study that shows 85.8% knows that low-fat diet is a reason of breast cancer. (Godfrey, Agatha, & Nankumbi, 2016) In our study, 55.7% participant knows that use of oral contraceptive is a reason of breast cancer but the study that was conducted in past shows that 83% participant gives correct responses (Madhukumar, Thambiran, Basavaraju, & Bedadala, 2017) In present study 65.1% participant gives a correct response that exposure of radiation is a risk factor for breast cancer. But the results were compared with the past study that shows 58.9% of participants gives the correct response. (Sama et al., 2017) In our study, the Sign and symptoms of breast cancer are large breasts (63.8%), Painless breast lump (67.1%) Nipple discharge (63.8%) Lump under the armpit (61.7%) Change in breast shape (69.1%) but the results are comparable with another study that was conducted in Cameroon shows that large breasts (57.2%), Painless breast lump (81.6%) Nipple discharge (54.6%) Lump under the armpit (22.7%) Change in breast shape (64.1%) (Sama et al., 2017) In present study practices was good 81.2% participant heard about breast self-examination. According to our study results, 59.1% of females perform breast self-examination. 4% of females said they start breast self-examination from next month. 10.1% of females perform breast self-examination once a month. The results were compared with the past study that shows 76.5% heard about breast self-examination 43.6% perform breast self-examination 38.3% said they start to perform from next month 44.9% said frequency of breast self-examination is once in a month (Godfrey, Agatha, & Nankumbi, 2016)

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